

THE PROBLEMS OF POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN PAKISTAN: A STUDY OF PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

This article examines the problems of policy implementation in Pakistan, a country where many good policies are made but often fail to achieve their real goals. This study focuses on issues that directly affect the common people and highlights how weak implementation creates a gap between policy design and actual practice. Examples are given to show how even well-planned programs could not bring results because of poor execution. The key questions that this paper aims to answer are: What are the main challenges to policy implementation in Pakistan? How do public institutions influence the implementation process? And what reforms are needed to policy outcomes in Pakistan? The findings show several barriers such as weak administrative capacity, lack of proper planning, political interference, poor coordination among government departments, corruption, limited participation of citizens, shortage of financial resources, and weak monitoring systems. These factors slow down progress and reduce public trust in institutions. The article concludes by giving some implications that could be considered for better results and help improve outcomes in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Policy implementation in a state simply means putting government decisions into actions. It ensures the process of turning plans and laws into services which plays a role in people's lives. In every state, the success of government policies does not only depend on how they are made but also how they are implemented. Like making of policy varies from country to country, the implementation of policies also varies. The implementation of policies is the only factor which affects and evaluates the proper functioning of a country. Like many other developing countries, Pakistan is facing very issue on a large scale on both federal and provincial levels. Despite having ambitious policies, Pakistan is consistently facing obstacles while implementing

these. Government often launches new policies with great optimism for the public, but most of the time many policies couldn't be able to implement in way they are portrayed (Grindle, 1980).

In Pakistan, while governments at both federal and provincial levels have introduced many policies focusing on enhancing sectors like education, health, poverty reduction, and energy, many of these policies have not produced the expected results. Many challenges can hinder the pure implementation of policies. These include weak institutions, corruption, political interferences and influences in institutions, lack of financial resources, weak infrastructure, and poor monitoring mechanism. Public institutions, which are majorly

responsible for the implementation of policies, are usually inefficient and lack the capacity to perform their roles. The key questions that this paper aims to answer are: What are the main challenges to policy implementation in Pakistan? How do public institutions influence the implementation process? And what reforms are needed to policy outcomes in Pakistan?

Methodology

The paper is based on qualitative research using secondary data. Sources include journals, articles, government reports, and publications from organizations like World Health Organizations and Pakistan Institute of Development Economics. The paper also includes case studies to support its findings. The goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the institutional problems affecting policy implementation.

Literature Review

There is plethora of work on policy implementation of different institutions in Pakistan. Several scholars have examined the reasons behind weak policy implementation in developing countries. Many writers wrote about the struggle of Pakistan in policy making and then implementing those policies in a fine way. Like Grindle (1980) emphasized that successful implementation requires clear goals, resources, and support from institutions. In Pakistan, these elements are often lacking. Cheema and Rondinelli (1983) argued that centralization and weak local institutions reduce the effectiveness of policies in developing countries like Pakistan. According to Sulaiman (2000), bureaucracy in Pakistan suffers from poor training, lack of motivation, and resistance to change. Corruption and political interference are also common, which limits the capacity of institutions to act in the public interest (PIDE, 2020). These findings are consistent with the view that weak institutions are a massive obstacle to successful policy implementation. Many factors are considered as responsible for policy failures, for example not having clarity of policies, pure commitment of leadership, governance structures, centralization, resource constraints. A policy is a planned method that helps the government to deal with public problems. It gives a

clear way to follow in order to reach future goals. According to Anderson (2010), public policy means a planned and purposeful action taken by an individual or a group of people to solve a specific issue in society. It is not just a simple decision. It is a process made with purpose to handle real problems faced by the public. The success of any policy does not depend only on how well it is made. It mostly depends on how well it is carried out. As Khan (2016) explains, policy implementation is a step-by-step method that follows clear instructions to achieve the goals and objectives of the policy. In other words, a good policy must also be followed by good actions, or it will not produce the desired results. Durlak and DuPre (2008) also say that a successful policy does not only need to be planned well but also needs to be implemented properly. This means that even the best-designed policy can fail if the people who are supposed to carry it out do not manage the process correctly. So, managing the work after the policy is made is just as important as writing the policy itself. In the field of education, both the writing (formulation) and carrying out (implementation) of policy are considered important. But in reality, this difference between the two is not clear. As a result, policies often do not reach their goals. This confusion makes it harder for policies to succeed, especially, Pakistan still faces many challenges in improving literacy and has not yet achieved its main education goals (Ahmad et al., 2012). Despite having all the policies in pocket, Pakistan is facing challenges when it comes to education of rural areas. This shows that even with policies in place, the lack of strong implementation can stop progress. Every developed country works on its education and health sector particularly. Pakistan educational sector also has many adorable policies while it struggles to implement even few of them and the constantly failure to achieve different aspects of educational improvement has caused concern among educationists (Ali, 2006). As Sial, Usman, Zulfiqar, Satti, and Khursheed (2013) argue that policy implementation should be the priority for the organization than the strategy formulation, because if the strategic plan is not successfully implemented by the staff and management, its cost and damages grow more than the failure of strategy formulation. Pakistan is a country with many different kinds of

people. There are many languages, traditions, and cultural values across the country. While this diversity is part of Pakistan's identity, it also brings problems when it comes to applying government policies in all areas. Policies that may work well in one region may not be accepted in another because of different beliefs and customs. One major example is policies that support women's rights or promote education for girls. In many areas of Pakistan, especially in conservative and rural regions, people may not agree with these policies. They may believe that women should stay at home or that girls should not go to school after a certain age. As Shaikh (2019) explains, policies that aim to improve women's status or increase their access to education often face strong opposition in such places. This resistance makes it hard to carry out these policies successfully. Ali (2020) also studied this issue and found clear examples of how cultural beliefs can stop progress. In his study, he looked at efforts to bring more girls into schools. The study found that in rural areas, these efforts did not work very well. Many families still believe that it is more important for girls to get married early than to continue their studies. Because of this, even though there were programs to help girls go to school, many families chose not to send their daughters. This shows that policies, even if well designed, cannot succeed without considering local culture and social values. So, the cultural diversity of Pakistan can become a barrier to policy success. A policy made at the national level must take into account the traditions and beliefs of the local communities. Without this understanding, policies may not be accepted or followed, especially in areas where people hold strong traditional views. As shown by both Shaikh (2019) and Ali (2020), cultural resistance plays a major role in the failure of certain policies, especially those related to gender and education. Like education problems, Pakistan is facing health sector problems at massive level as well. Even though many health policies have been introduced in Pakistan, the country still faces serious problems in the health sector. People in Pakistan have a low life expectancy, and many children and adults suffer from malnutrition. These problems continue because health policies are not implemented properly. One major issue is that resources are not used wisely. According to (Jabeen

et al., 2016), another problem is the lack of cooperation between the federal and provincial governments, there are weak systems for checking and tracking progress in the health sector. A clear example of these problems is the ongoing battle against polio. Even though several campaigns have been carried out to eliminate the disease, polio has still not been fully removed from the country. This shows that poor planning, weak teamwork between government departments, and not enough resources are serious issues in Pakistan's health system (Khan, 2025).

18th Amendment to the Constitution of Pakistan is also considered as obstacle of policy implementation. 18th Amendment was passed in 2010. This was a major legal change that gave more power to the provinces. Before this amendment, the federal government controlled many important areas such as health, education, and local development. The goal of the 18th Amendment was to improve governance by giving provinces the authority to make their own decisions. It was expected that local governments would better understand the needs of their people and could take quicker and more effective actions. According to Ahmed (2016), the results were not as good as expected. Many provinces were not ready to handle these new responsibilities. They lacked the proper systems, trained staff, and financial resources needed to manage the new powers. As a result, even though they were given more control, they could not use it properly. There was also poor coordination between the federal and provincial governments. Important tasks often got delayed or were not done at all because the roles and responsibilities were not clearly shared between different levels of government. The main reason for the weak implementation of the 18th Amendment was the lack of capacity at the provincial level. The provinces did not have strong institutions or skilled workers to manage the new duties. Additionally, communication between the central and provincial governments was weak. Instead of working together, both sides often blamed each other when problems came up. This poor coordination made it difficult to bring real improvements in public service delivery. Ahmad (2023) says that the unique political history and various forms of government in Pakistan have

created many factors that influence the country's policy-making process. To understand how policies are made in Pakistan, it is important to consider both internal and external factors. Studies from both inside and outside Pakistan show that many different factors influence how policies are made and developed. Just like in other countries, Pakistan's policy-making process is shaped by many forces. These include the knowledge, skills, and experience of the people making the policies, the roles of those involved in the policy process, and the country's legal system, such as the constitution. Other important factors include social and cultural traditions, political events, natural disasters, the economy, religious beliefs, pressure groups, and the power of national institutions (Torres, 1989). In Pakistan, institutions like the bureaucracy, military, and political parties have a strong impact on how policies are made. This is mainly due to Pakistan's special political history. After gaining independence from British rule, Pakistan inherited a bureaucratic system that was based on the British colonial model (Chaudry, 2011). This system had been used in the Indian subcontinent by the British to keep control over the region (Kamran, 2008). It followed Max Weber's ideas of bureaucracy, which included command, fairness, chances for promotion, and good salaries. These features helped civil servants to deliver public services in an organized and efficient way. Although there were only a few Muslim officers in the British-era Indian Superior Services, they were highly trained and had strong skills to run the government effectively (Chaudry, 2011). After independence, Pakistan had many serious problems and very few resources—especially not enough trained people. However, the small number of bureaucrats managed the situation well because of their training and experience. Their early success helped the bureaucracy become a very powerful institution in Pakistan (Jeffrey, 1994). Even though Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah, reminded civil servants in his 1948 speech at the Staff College that they were supposed to serve the public, things changed over time (Chaudry, 2011). The political structure that developed after independence gave more and more power to bureaucrats, turning them into decision-makers instead of just implementers. In theory, politicians are supposed to make public

policies, and bureaucrats are expected to carry them out. This is how it works in developed democracies. But in Pakistan, bureaucrats often make as well as implement policies. This happens because bureaucrats usually have more experience, education, and training than elected officials (Javaid, 2010). The political class in Pakistan has come to depend heavily on the bureaucracy because many politicians lack the necessary skills to govern effectively. However, this close relationship has created some problems. Politicians have sometimes used the bureaucracy for their own personal gain. This has weakened the independence of the civil service and affected its performance. Also, during times of military rule, the army has relied on the bureaucracy to help run the government. This further increased the bureaucracy's power and made its role more permanent and difficult to challenge. . In addition to this, (Lipsky, 1980) looks at the role of people who work directly with the public, like teachers, health workers, or local officers. These people are called street-level bureaucrats. The theory says that these workers have a lot of power because they make choices based on what they know about the policy and the local situation. In Pakistan, these workers often face problems like not having enough training or tools. This makes it hard for them to follow and apply the policies properly specially in rural areas where they lack infrastructure of offices even. Most of Pakistani districts are still facing Wadera System where government officials face intervention from elites of very areas. A study by Qureshi (2015) found that Pakistan's public institutions often lack clear procedures for policy implementation. For instance, the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP), a major social welfare policy, faced delays because local offices lacked the technology and staff to process applications efficiently. In this program, people used to get their money and had to stand in lines for hours and hours, and got sometimes half of their actual amount particularly in villages. Like this, One example is the Ehsaas Program. This program started in 2019 to help poor people in Pakistan. Many people said the plan was good and had a strong design. It was made to give money and support to people who needed help. The idea behind the program was kind and useful. But when the program

started, many problems came up. Some people took money through corruption. There were also delays, and many people did not get the money on time. Some people did not even know they could get help because they were not informed. Because of these problems, the program could not work well (Siddiqui, 2021).

Key Problems in Policy Implementation

1. Lack of Planning Policy

Policy implementation fails in Pakistan for the many times because of poor planning. Policies are sometimes created without looking at realistic timelines, consequences, financial analysis, or clear responsibilities. Most of policies lack implementation strategies, which causes confusion among implementing policies. Policy makers make policy with over optimism without thinking about the consequences and results. New governments come and try to make many policies in order to have the sympathy of masses. But eventually, many policies fail to be accomplished due to weak planning of policy (Grindle, 1980).

2. Weak Institutional Capacity

Most of Pakistani institutions don't have such capacity to implement the policies according to needs of society. They lack trained staff, financial resources, proper management, and technical knowledge. Health and education sectors in rural areas are massively struggling in this regard. There are schools but there is no availability of resources over there, like stationery, books for children, even teachers don't usually come. Same is the situation of health sector particularly in rural areas where there is no availability of equipments, technical tools, trained staff and knowledge of matters (Siddique, 2016). Poor service quality, and incomplete programs often result from challenges such as weak institutional capacity, massive issues, and unforeseen events like the COVID-19 pandemic (World Bank, 2020).

3. Corruption

Corruption is widespread in many government departments. Funds meant for public welfare are often misused. This reduces the impact of public programs and increases distrust among citizens.

Corruption is a big problem in Pakistan. It slows down economic growth and stops the country from moving forward. When government officials misuse power for personal gain, public money is wasted, and important services like education, health, and transport suffer. This affects poor people the most, as they depend on these services. This hinders, on a large scale, the implementation of policies in institutions as officials are more centered towards filling their banks (Shaikh & Khan, 2023).

4. Political Interference

In Pakistan, political interference plays a big role in the way policies are made and carried out. Many political leaders use public policies to gain short-term benefits, such as winning public support or strengthening their position in the government. This very thing hinders the actual purpose of these policies, which is to serve the public. Instead of focusing on long-term development or solving the real problems faced by the people, policies are sometimes shaped to meet political goals. This kind of interference damages the process of implementation and leads to poor or uneven results (Khan, 2016). For instance, politicians may push for development projects such as roads, hospitals, schools, or electricity schemes only in areas where they have strong voter support. These decisions are not always based on need or fairness but on the desire to win votes and stay in power. As a result, regions that are politically less important or support rival parties may be ignored, even if they are in greater need of services (Javed, 2020). A major example of this issue can be seen in the implementation of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). While this project was meant to bring economic growth to the entire country, political preferences influenced how the projects under CPEC were distributed. Some provinces or cities received more investment, while others were left behind. This uneven planning and resource allocation caused tensions and raised questions about fairness and transparency in government decisions. Also, politicians with winning party try their best influence bureaucracy of their own districts to maintain their influence. They ask secretariate to appoint Deputy commissioners, CEOs of their willing and support, so that they would obey

them after their appointment. This interference harms the merit of policies. It also creates inequality, as only selected people benefit while others remain ignored. This not only reduces the effectiveness of policies but also increases mistrust among citizens toward the government.

Political Instability and Discontinuity

Political instability is a major issue in Pakistan. The country has seen sudden changes in leadership, early elections, and sometimes even military takeovers. Since Pakistan's independence, no prime minister has been able to complete a full five-year term. This constant change in leadership makes it difficult to keep policies running smoothly from one government to the next (Khan, 2025). Because of this, many important development projects are either stopped halfway, changed, or forgotten when a new government takes over. This lack of political stability creates serious problems for government institutions. It becomes hard for them to plan ahead or stick to long-term goals. For example, when a new political party comes into power, it may cancel or change the development policies made by the previous government. This results in confusion, mixed priorities, and poor implementation (Khan, 2025). Policies that could have helped the country in the long run are often ignored because new leaders focus on quick results that help them stay in power. Even when policies are carefully designed and have the potential to bring positive change, they often fail because of this unstable political environment. Without political consistency and long-term commitment, it becomes nearly impossible to carry out major reforms or development plans that require time and effort. As each new government tries to promote its own agenda, the overall progress of the country suffers.

Lack of Coordination

In Pakistan, one of the biggest problems in policy implementation is the poor coordination between different government departments and institutions. Many times, various agencies and ministries do not work together properly. This creates ambiguity, delays, and weak results (Malik, 2018). When government offices do not share information, do not plan together, or do not follow the same goals, the

policies cannot be carried out in an effective way. A clear example of this problem is the National Action Plan (NAP), which was created to fight terrorism. Although the plan was very important, it did not work as expected because there was a lack of cooperation among key departments. The police, military, and intelligence agencies did not always share information or coordinate their actions. This caused delays and weakened the overall impact of the plan (Rehman, 2021). Instead of acting as a team, each department followed its own direction, which slowed down the fight against terrorism. Another area where coordination is weak is between the federal and provincial governments. After the 18th Amendment, many powers were given to the provinces, including control over education. However, this shift created problems, as both federal and provincial authorities sometimes disagree or do not work together smoothly. For example, education policies are often poorly implemented because provinces do not always get enough support or clear guidelines from the federal government. These disagreements and overlaps make it hard to follow a single, united policy.

Weak Monitoring and Accountability

For a policy to work well, it is very important to have a strong system that can check how the policy is being used, find problems, and make changes when needed. This system is called monitoring and evaluation (M&E). In Pakistan, these systems are often weak or not properly used. Because of this, there is little accountability, and many policies are not fully or correctly implemented (Shah & Bukhari, 2019). When there is no proper way to check progress, it becomes easy for people in power to misuse their authority. Sometimes, policies are changed or ignored to suit personal or political interests. There is also a lack of independent offices or watchdogs that can check whether policies are being followed fairly. Without open and clear reporting systems, it is difficult to know what went wrong or who is responsible when a policy fails (Khan, 2025).

Limited Public Participation

In Pakistan, ordinary people are not often involved in making public policies. Most decisions are taken by officials and politicians without asking local communities for their views or needs. This lack of public participation means that many policies do not match what people actually want or require in their daily lives (Hassan, 2017).

A clear example of this problem can be seen in Karachi's urban development projects. In several cases, the government started large development plans without asking the people living in poor areas for their input. As a result, many of these low-income communities were ignored in the planning process. This led to strong resistance from residents and caused several projects to fail or face serious delays (Qazi, 2022).

When people are not part of the policy process, they feel left out and may even reject the projects meant to help them. It also reduces trust in government institutions. Public participation is important because local people often have useful knowledge and ideas that can improve the success of a policy. If they are included from the beginning, policies are more likely to be accepted and properly implemented.

To improve public participation, Pakistan needs better systems that allow citizens to share their opinions and give feedback during the planning and implementation stages of policies. This will make policies more inclusive, relevant, and likely to succeed.

Economic Constraints

Pakistan faces serious economic problems that limit its ability to carry out public policies. The country has a large national debt, rising inflation, and low income from taxes. These financial difficulties mean that the government often does not have enough money to spend on important programs (Husain, 2020). Because of this, even well-designed policies remain incomplete or are never started. For example, policies that promise big improvements—like free healthcare for everyone, require a lot of money and planning. However, due to the country's limited budget, such policies are often announced but never put into action (Khan, 2019). These kinds of programs need regular and large amounts of

funding, which Pakistan's economy cannot provide at the moment. Economic constraints also affect service delivery. Schools, hospitals, and transport systems do not receive the resources they need to function properly. When budgets are low, salaries for public workers are delayed, and supplies like medicines or teaching materials become scarce. This weakens the entire system and causes policies to fail, even when they are based on good ideas.

Implications

The paper talks about many problems and gives solutions for them. It focuses on the specific issues that were noticed during careful study. These problems were looked at closely, and the paper explains how to fix them in a clear and simple way. Each solution is designed to help make things better by tackling the issues step by step. The goal is to provide answers that work and are straightforward, so anyone can follow them. By addressing these problems, the paper helps people find ways to improve situations that were not working well. It shows how careful thinking and clear ideas can lead to good solutions. There are many problems but the solutions to the problems which were observed and addressed in the paper listed below.

Mandatory Planning Framework

Develop a mandatory planning framework for all policies. This framework should require policymakers to set realistic timelines, conduct detailed financial assessments, and assign clear roles to departments. Establish a dedicated policy planning unit in each ministry to create detailed implementation strategies before policies are approved. Train policymakers to use data-driven tools, like cost-benefit analysis, to predict outcomes and avoid over-optimism. To address frequent policy changes by new governments, form an independent policy review board to evaluate and approve policies based on long-term benefits, not political motives. For example, a health policy could include a step-by-step plan with budget estimates and staff assignments to ensure clarity and feasibility.

Invest in capacity-building Programs

Government should provide regular training for staff in rural schools and hospitals, focusing on skills

like digital record-keeping and basic medical procedures. Partner with NGOs or international organizations to fund essential resources, such as books, stationery, and medical equipment. It should create mobile training units to reach rural areas, ensuring teachers and health workers are equipped to deliver services. Introduce performance-based incentives to motivate staff attendance and accountability.

Anti-corruption Measures

Government should strengthen anti-corruption measures by establishing independent audit committees to monitor fund usage in real-time. Use digital platforms for transparent financial transactions, such as online portals for project budgets, to reduce cash-based bribery. Encourage public reporting of corruption by setting up anonymous hotlines with legal protections for whistleblowers. Launch community awareness campaigns to educate citizens on their rights to public funds, empowering them to demand accountability. For example, a public health program could publish its budget online, allowing citizens to track spending and report discrepancies.

Reduce Political Interference

Government should focus on reducing political interference by creating independent oversight bodies to monitor policy implementation. These bodies should ensure projects are allocated based on need, not political favouritism. Enforce merit-based appointments for key positions like deputy commissioners by setting strict, transparent criteria through a public service commission. Limit policy changes by requiring new governments to justify alterations to existing plans through public consultations. For example, CPEC projects could be reviewed by a neutral committee to ensure fair distribution across provinces, reducing regional tensions and ensuring equity.

Establish a National Policy Continuity Framework

Pakistan has faced surprise governmental shifts across its whole history. In order to enhance its implementation of policies, it should establish a national policy continuity framework that requires all governments to commit to key long-term policies,

such as education or infrastructure plans, for at least a decade. Create a bipartisan policy council with representatives from major parties to agree on core development goals that remain unchanged despite leadership shifts. Use public reporting to track policy progress, making it harder for new governments to abandon projects without justification. For instance, a multi-year education reform plan could be protected by law, ensuring it continues regardless of who is in power.

Set Up Inter-Departmental Task Forces

Setting up inter-departmental task forces for major policies, with regular meetings to align goals and share information, can help Pakistan in developing its policy implementation process. It should develop a centralized digital platform to track policy progress and allow real-time updates across agencies. For federal-provincial coordination, create joint committees to clarify roles and provide clear guidelines, especially for devolved sectors like education. For example, the National Action Plan could use a shared database where police, military, and intelligence agencies log actions, ensuring unified efforts against terrorism.

Strengthen Monitoring

Strengthening monitoring by creating independent evaluation units within each ministry to track policy progress using clear metrics, like project completion rates would also be a productive step in this regard. Pakistan should publish quarterly progress reports online to ensure transparency and public accountability. Train staff to use simple monitoring tools, such as mobile apps, to collect real-time data from project sites. Establish independent watchdog agencies with the power to investigate and penalize policy deviations. For example, a rural health policy could use a mobile app to report medicine shortages, ensuring quick fixes and accountability.

Involve Communities

Involve communities in policy planning through public consultations, town hall meetings, and surveys before projects start. Create local advisory groups in areas like Karachi to ensure residents' needs are considered. Use social media and local radio to gather feedback from rural and low-income

communities. Educate citizens on how to participate through community workshops. For example, a Karachi development project could hold open forums with residents to discuss plans, reducing resistance and ensuring policies meet local needs.

Conclusion

In wrapping up this study on policy implementation challenges in Pakistan, it's clear that turning government plans into real actions is a tough task. The paper explored how Pakistan struggles to make its policies work, despite having bold ideas for improving education, health, poverty reduction, and other areas. The main hurdles—weak institutions, corruption, political interference, poor coordination, and limited resources—create a gap between what policies promise and what they deliver. These issues affect people's lives, leaving many without the services they need, like proper schools or healthcare. By looking at examples like the Ehsaas Program, the Benazir Income Support Program, and efforts to promote girls' education, we see how good intentions often fall short due to practical problems. One big takeaway is that weak planning sets policies up to fail from the start. When policymakers don't set clear timelines, assign roles, or think about costs, confusion takes over. For instance, programs like Ehsaas faced delays and corruption because the plans didn't account for local challenges or staff shortages. This shows that policies need realistic strategies, not just big promises. Institutions also need better tools and training to do their jobs. Rural schools and hospitals often lack books, equipment, or trained workers, which stops policies from reaching people who need them most. Adding to this, corruption eats away at funds meant for public welfare, making citizens lose trust in the government.

Political interference and instability make things worse. Leaders often push projects that help them win votes rather than solve real problems, like when CPEC projects favored certain areas over others. Frequent changes in government also disrupt long-term plans, as new leaders scrap old policies to promote their own. This lack of continuity means projects like health campaigns or school reforms rarely finish as planned. Poor coordination between departments and between federal and provincial

governments creates more roadblocks. The National Action Plan's struggles against terrorism show how agencies working separately can weaken even the most urgent policies.

Cultural and economic challenges add another layer of difficulty. In diverse regions, policies like girls' education face resistance because they don't align with local traditions. Without involving communities in planning, policies often miss the mark. Economically, Pakistan's debt and low tax revenue limit funding for big ideas like free healthcare. Even when policies are announced, there's often no money to back them up, leaving schools and hospitals understaffed and under-equipped. To fix these issues, Pakistan needs practical steps. First, policies must start with clear, realistic plans that include budgets and timelines. A dedicated planning unit in each ministry could help make this happen. Second, institutions need more support—training for staff, better equipment, and incentives to keep workers motivated. Third, fighting corruption with transparent systems, like online budget tracking, can ensure funds reach the right places. Reducing political interference by setting up independent oversight bodies would help policies focus on public needs, not political gains. A national framework to protect key policies from being dropped by new governments could ensure long-term progress. Better coordination through shared platforms and task forces would make agencies work as a team, while stronger monitoring systems would catch problems early. Finally, involving citizens through town halls or surveys would make policies more relevant and accepted, especially in diverse areas. These changes won't be easy, but they're necessary for Pakistan to move forward. Policies can only succeed if they're planned well, supported by strong institutions, and carried out with honesty and teamwork. By addressing these challenges, Pakistan can turn its ambitious goals into real improvements for its people. This study shows that while the problems are big, they're not impossible to solve. With commitment and practical reforms, the government can build a system where policies don't just stay on paper but actually change lives for the better.

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